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Doubling the voice: what can be learned from observing public social critique in China

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Key findings

- Social critique in China does not necessarily entail wishes for regime change. People can be highly critical of the social reality and still wholeheartedly support the Chinese Communist Party (CCP).
- The CCP has all means to exert total control over public discourse, but chooses to allow a certain level of public critique. This helps the CCP identify problems early, act swiftly and preventively to ease people's anger or worries.
- Chinese citizens are well aware of the high social cost of individual dissent. Therefore, most people prefer to keep their critique of the social reality within bounds tolerated by the state. Open dissent is highly marginal, lacks agency, and will most likely remain so.
- It is culturally and socially acceptable for individuals to maintain double identities – voicing views in line with the official discourse when in office, and holding views critical of the state and its policies when speaking in private. Dialogue by the EU with Chinese counterparts should be maintained in “spaces of mutual benevolence”. The EU should acknowledge the ambivalent positions these individuals may hold.
- The EU should acknowledge that the unique, authoritarian political system in China is unlikely to change in the short term. Anti-CCP press coverage and anti-CCP political attitudes in the EU are not conducive to sustaining a friendly living environment for Chinese migrants in Europe, nor to developing a mode of relations with the PRC that can prove beneficial to the EU.
- To accurately understand and efficiently assess the relationship between the CCP and the population of the PRC, it is crucial for the EU to learn more about the social reality in China, rather than focus solely on the political regime.

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Introduction

It is a generally accepted fact that the last decade of Xi Jinping's rule is marked by increased politicisation, which, more than before, imposes conformity in public discourse and diminishes spaces for freedom of expression in the PRC. Chinese society is often viewed from the outside as under a tight grip of the totalitarian regime, exerted by means of mass surveillance, omnipresent censorship, and control of public and private discourse through sophisticated, technological means. The population is considered completely deprived of a voice and the capacity to provide criticism. In this Policy Brief, we attempt to show that the situation is far more complex. The analyses of Chinese social reality and the way it is portrayed in art and culture point to a high level of acceptance of the policies of the state by the Chinese population, and at the same time show patterns of critique and high social engagement on the part of many individuals who identify numerous problems and pinpoint their causes, without an ambition for regime change.

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Critique without a political change agenda

Social critique in China has by no means been eradicated by the state. On the contrary, social media, voices of experts, intellectuals and other public figures, as well as works of artists and writers show a wealth of content that is critical, and sometimes even sharply so, of the Chinese reality.

Several notable examples illustrate this phenomenon especially clearly on Chinese social media. The discourse of “lying flat” (*tangping*) that gained traction in 2021, along with the subsequent neologism “runxue” (“runology” - emigrating from China for study or other purposes), quickly went viral. These catchphrases reflect **young people's resistance to relentless competition and social pressure**, and a wish for a different life than that of the previous generation: working less, having more time for themselves and more freedom to decide on the lifestyle they want to lead. During the Shanghai lockdown of 2022, the widely shared video “Voices of April” captured real audio recordings of residents, vividly conveying widespread anxiety and anger while resonating with a broad audience. That same year, the “Iron Chain Mother” incident in Xuzhou spread rapidly across platforms like Douyin and Weibo, sparking fierce criticism of women's rights violations, human trafficking, and local governance failures. Similarly, the Chinese #MeToo movement since 2018, and heated debates over the exploitative “996” work schedule have revealed a collective reckoning with gender inequality and labour oppression. Recently, school bullying sparked a series of protests among parents and a huge reaction on social media.

Although many of these online expressions are swiftly deleted and those voicing them sometimes face repercussions, **such critique nevertheless manages to gain wide circulation and generate intense debate within short timeframes.** Without directly demanding political change, these expressions still demonstrate the persistence of public engagement and critical awareness of China's contemporary social realities.

Netizens have developed creative strategies to circumvent censorship, employing homophones, pinyin substitutions, cultural metaphors, and satirical memes to convey critical messages.

In Chinese literature, performative and visual arts, authors and creators continue to test the limits of artistic freedom, taking on such seemingly controversial topics as public surveillance, family and personal dramas brought about through the Chinese model of economic development, corruption and abuse of power in politics, or the disillusionment of youth who cease to believe in the shared future. Each of these topics could theoretically lead to questioning the leadership of the CCP, but artists are usually careful to contain their critique; they focus on local problems, portray lower-ranking officials, recount personal stories in some remote locations, which do not suggest any generalisations. At the same time, **social critique is cloaked in metaphor, allusion, and humour.** Audiences learn to understand what is not said, and what remains hidden.

There is space for voicing critique also in academia - through generous research projects focusing on social problems. One example of such a project is research on the crisis of Chinese youth. The authorities considered it serious enough to arouse the interest of scholars, resulting in numerous papers revealing material and ideological changes among young people. Such critique is permitted, as **research helps the authorities assess the shortcomings of certain policies and decisions, and consider policy adjustments.**

The usefulness of tolerating critique for the CCP

Social and political critique is tolerated by the authorities (up to a point) for several reasons. Firstly, such a critique functions like a **safety valve, preventing the dangerous build-up of anger and frustration.** If people can ridicule or harshly criticise some public figures in private without getting punished, strong, negative emotions get ventilated. Especially social media are such spaces where some level of freedom of speech is tolerated as long as it does not lead to the birth of any movement or a formulation of any specific political agenda.

A typical example is the rise of "Kong Yiji Literature" on Chinese social media in 2023. Drawing on Lu Xun's character who "could not take off his long gown," many young people used this literary reference to describe the predicament of university graduates who discovered that **higher education, rather than opening opportunities, had become a burden.** The phrase spread rapidly, accumulating hundreds of millions of views on Weibo and Douyin while sparking widespread resonance and debate. As the discussion gained momentum, the official Communist Youth League account criticised young people for being "self-pitying" and "choosing to degenerate," and attributed Kong Yiji's tragedy to individual failings. This official response provoked strong backlash among young netizens, many of whom accused official outlets of condescension and deflecting attention from structural problems. The debate quickly expanded into broader discussions about diminishing social mobility, with some commentators describing the state media's rhetoric, and by extension, the government's stance, as "gaslighting." Although the topic was eventually censored, it briefly captured generational anxieties and signalled the urgency of relieving employment-related pressures to both society and the state.

A similar pattern emerged in debates over delayed retirement throughout 2024. In February, when an expert proposed raising the retirement age for women to 60, netizens directly criticised him as “out of touch with ordinary people” and questioned the reliability of his data. By July, a viral rumour claiming that “all those born in the 1990s would have to work until 65” circulated widely, prompting jokes about “working in old age” and speculation that the rumour represented a government “test of public opinion.” However, when the new retirement policy was formally announced in September, online discourse shifted dramatically: comment sections on major news outlets and official accounts contained almost exclusively supportive remarks and thumbs-up emoji, while earlier satire and criticism had vanished.

These episodes reveal a recurring dynamic in Chinese social media discourse: when policies remain undefined or issues ambiguous, public discussion tends to be relatively open, with dissatisfaction expressed through humour, metaphor, or criticism targeting individual experts. Once an official policy line is established, however, the space for public debate contracts rapidly, producing an appearance of consensus. This **rhythm of initial openness followed by sudden constraint** allows social media to function as a limited “safety valve” while simultaneously reinforcing public awareness of boundaries that cannot be crossed.

The second reason for tolerating public critique is **its usefulness for the state to identify problems before they can disrupt the social order**. This is not limited to social media content and its analyses by the authorities. Scholars are encouraged to conduct genuine social research because the authorities need to know what is happening in China. This also includes pinpointing needs of reform, such as advocating for more initiatives in terms of employment, subsidies for children, social production, reforms in enterprise and administration management, or mental health, targeting especially young people. These are valuable outputs for the authorities to consider. However, there are limits to the criticism the researchers can express. They must speak the “truth” but they must do so using a very specific and carefully drafted language.

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The third reason is **exerting pressure on local officials to act**. The organisation of the Chinese state leaves considerable power and independence to local authorities. The central level has limited leverage on policy execution and everyday management lower down the administrative ladder. And yet, it is particularly concerned with resolving problems at the grassroots level. As there are no representatives of the central government there, it is difficult for Beijing to obtain reliable information about the specific actions of local authorities and the degree of population satisfaction. **Criticism and expression of discontent by the inhabitants put local officials in an uneasy limelight, and in this way force them to act**. Such criticism and protest at the grassroots level can actually help the central government execute some policies locally. For example, while provincial or municipal officials might find it beneficial to protect local industry and let it pollute the environment unchecked, protests by inhabitants amplified by social media create pressure which helps to enforce national environmental protection standards. In July 2022, hundreds of people attended protests against banks that had frozen their deposits. Beijing authorities acted quickly to solve the problem, investigating several local officials and local banks.

The price of venturing beyond the unwritten red lines

The social cost of individual dissidence is very high. The big stories covered by foreign media outlets usually concern journalists or activists imprisoned for brave social actions or sharp critique of the state. The convicts get many-year prison sentences, their families are targeted by the police, their lives crushed by the ruthless system. **For the vast majority of the Chinese population the risk of facing such severe oppression is low.** However, ordinary citizens who voice their critique or attempt to participate in social movements not sanctioned by the authorities often face other, less visible forms of punishment: loss of employment, expulsion from school, constant difficulties in dealing with officials, and social exclusion.

With so much life and social interaction happening in China now through social media, **a simple blocking of someone's WeChat account suffices to paralyse that person's everyday activity.** No contact with friends, no means to purchase their favourite goods online, loss of access to countless online services, difficulties to get by in a country where WeChat plays multiple functions from communication, payments to personal identification – such punishment for many people would be difficult to accept.

For those who use social media for professional purposes, blocking accounts, or in especially serious cases, deleting them altogether, is even more disastrous. For public figures, be them actors, comedians or musicians, this means disappearing from view and losing their position on a very competitive market. For influencers and online retailers, this not only means losing their hard-built recognition and precious network of clients and viewers, but also a sudden loss of income. It is very hard to start from scratch, and not many people are prepared for this.

And so, we can consider dissidents as heroes, deserving respect and support, but we have to take into account the fact that, in the absence of public and massive discontent, **dissidence remains highly marginal in China.** The A4 Movement (also known as the “White Sheet Movement”), the sweeping protests that took place in late November 2022 against the “zero-COVID” policy may serve as a rare example of partly-organised and non-sanctioned protest that took place under a very specific set of conditions.

Most people who have critical views of the social reality in China choose to negotiate their critique within the invisible lines of what is tolerated by the state, sometimes testing these limits, but proceeding carefully. They are well aware that there is much at stake in terms of their careers and personal situation. Moreover, even in terms of efficiency, becoming a dissident is perceived by most people as counterproductive. As dissidents, they would be symbolically expelled from the community, and lose influence.

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Double identities

Public individuals in China develop what can be called “double identities”. In their official or public roles, they express views in accord with the party line. Very often, they quote whole phrases from the official party documents, and adopt expressions from party discourse in their speech. Be it the Taiwan issue, Chinese policies towards Russia and Ukraine, or the critique of US support of Israel – voices of experts, officials and scholars, especially in the presence of

foreigners, tend to align with what can be heard in Xi Jinping's speeches. However, the very same individuals might express significantly differing views when in private: meeting with friends, family and sometimes colleagues. In a private setting, they can be quite outspoken in their critique of certain policies or even the fundamentals of the Chinese state, contradicting what they say in public.

This double identity is socially accepted as a way of negotiating between private views and official roles: contradicting messages from the same individual are not viewed as surprising or morally ambiguous. Messages are understood as part of a social situation in which they are produced – they are not always about conveying truth, but about fulfilling the expectations linked to one's social role.

And so, numerous Chinese public figures are neither pro-CCP nor anti-CCP. They accept the Chinese political reality and adapt to it in order to manage their everyday lives. When they are asked to show loyalty to the state, they comply. When they meet in private, they feel comfortable expressing their personal views which might go directly against what they say in public. To borrow from an influential work by Albert O. Hirschman (1970), they constantly negotiate between loyalty (to the CCP and the PRC), voice (i.e. voicing their critique), and exit (leaving the country, changing their lives completely).

Recommendations

Chinese discourse of the Xi Jinping era is not devoid of voices of critique – whether in expert circles, social media or in literary texts and cultural productions. **Much of this critique concentrates on domestic policies at the local level or social issues important for ordinary citizens.** Rarely can one find critique with a political agenda, and as long as the critical discourse doesn't undermine the CCP's position, it allows space (and freedom) for such expressions of views without any punitive measures. Part of the discourse landscape are "double identities" of individuals who seem to hold different views and positions in public and in private contexts, which should be understood as a way to negotiate between loyalty, voice, and exit (Hirschman 1970). This ambivalence of "double identities" should not tempt the EU to push their Chinese counterparts to take a definite stand.

The EU should make sure it has the capacity and policies to educate new generations of China analysts who understand historic and cultural contexts

The EU should acknowledge that **the unique, authoritarian political system in China is unlikely to change in the short term**, due to the lack of political alternatives. Also the strategies of individuals or small groups of people who negotiate between loyalty and voice in this system will remain. Therefore, we propose a set of approaches which acknowledge this social fact and which might help in more effective personal communication with Chinese individuals and the society at large:

- Anti-CCP press coverage and anti-CCP political attitudes in the EU are not conducive to sustaining a friendly living environment for Chinese migrants in Europe, nor to

developing a mode of relations with the PRC that can prove beneficial to the EU. **It is advisable for the EC and the EU national authorities not to support such rhetoric, and deal with China in a pragmatic way**, remembering that many Chinese, even migrants from the PRC in Europe, hold ambivalent views towards the political system in China. For many Chinese people the question of a possible regime change is linked with concerns about unpredictable or even dangerous personal consequences for themselves that such a change could entail.

- Dialogue by EU officials with Chinese counterparts should be maintained in deliberately constructed **“spaces of mutual benevolence”**, where moral judgments are limited to the minimum, and where interlocutors focus on common traits and commonly-shared values, rather than on cultural differences. The EU should acknowledge ambivalent (and often contradictory) positions these individuals may hold. **Accepting the differences in opinions, judgments and values helps move the agenda forward.** In such “protective zones” of dialogue, sides should focus on sustaining relationships and exchange without insisting on political/ideological consistency. Criticism within “spaces of mutual benevolence” should serve stability and dialogue, not subversion.
- EU officials should refrain from making judgments on the level of internalisation of CCP discourse by their specific Chinese counterparts. Such judgments are rarely accurate, as “double identities” are common.
- The EU should support people-to-people contacts and exchanges with China, including senior officials. They, too, may exercise their “double identities”, especially when given proper buffer zones to do so.
- The EU should make sure it has the capacity and policies to educate new generations of China analysts who understand historic and cultural contexts, as well as the specificity of building and maintaining relations with the Chinese. The EU should, therefore, support Chinese language and society instruction in the European Higher Education Area and research on Chinese society, so that such new generations of analysts and experts can be educated to serve the EU.

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